

Longitudinal Observations of Cohabitation Dynamics and Growth in Captive Central Bearded
Dragons (*Pogona vitticeps*)

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December 2025

Abstract

Reptile social behavior is often described as limited and inflexible, with bearded dragons (*Pogona vitticeps*) commonly classified as a solitary species. This observational study examined the growth and behavioral dynamics of three bearded dragons from different hatches raised together in captivity over a 13-month period. Individuals were monitored for changes in behavior, social tolerance, and body mass across development. During the first 6–7 months, all three dragons cohabitated without overt aggression, injury, or suppression of growth, sharing basking sites, food resources, and space. As sexual maturity approached, the male began exhibiting dominance and reproductive behaviors toward the females, at which point he was removed to prevent stress and potential harm. Notably, prior to separation, the male displayed repeated agonistic behaviors toward an unfamiliar male approaching the enclosure, while showing tolerance toward the two familiar females. Following separation, the females continued to cohabitate successfully for the remainder of the study, while the male maintained healthy growth in isolation. Short-term reintroductions demonstrated continued tolerance among familiar individuals during feeding and basking. These observations suggest that while bearded dragons are not obligately social, tolerance and selective defensive behaviors toward familiar conspecifics may occur under specific captive conditions. Behavioral changes preceded any physiological decline, highlighting the importance of behavioral monitoring in captive husbandry and welfare assessments.

Introduction

Central Bearded Dragons (*Pogona vitticeps*) are increasingly popular as companion animals, leading to growing interest in their care and management in captive environments. Traditionally, bearded dragons are described as solitary reptiles, with social interactions in the wild largely limited to territorial defense, dominance displays, and reproduction. Males, in particular, are known to exhibit strong territorial behavior, and cohabitation is therefore generally discouraged due to the risk of aggression and injury (Vitt & Caldwell, 2013). These assumptions have contributed to the widespread view that bearded dragons are incapable of sustained social interaction in captivity.

However, recent research has begun to challenge the notion that reptiles are behaviorally rigid or strictly solitary. Social behavior is increasingly recognized as existing along a continuum rather than as a binary trait, even among species traditionally classified as asocial or non-social (Brakes et al., 2019). Studies have demonstrated that reptiles can exhibit behavioral flexibility, including the ability to adapt to novel environments, alter behavioral strategies, and respond to changes in ecological conditions such as those imposed by captivity (Leal & Powell, 2012). These findings suggest that social tolerance and context-dependent interactions may be more common in reptiles than previously assumed. Despite this shift in perspective, long-term observational data on reptile social dynamics remain limited. Longitudinal studies examining social tolerance and cohabitation over extended developmental periods are relatively uncommon, even within managed settings such as zoos and aquariums where systematic behavioral data collection is possible (Wilkinson et al., 2025). As a result, the effects of captivity on social interactions, especially across developmental stages, remain poorly documented for many reptile species, including bearded dragons.

Given the limited understanding of bearded dragon social dynamics, it is important to investigate how captive conditions may alter ecological pressures and influence social tolerance over time. The purpose of this study was to examine whether juvenile bearded dragons can exhibit sustained social tolerance when raised together in captivity and to assess how social dynamics change with the onset of sexual maturity.

Methods

Study Design

This study was a longitudinal observational study conducted over a 13-month period to examine growth and behavioral dynamics in captive bearded dragons.

Subjects

Three juvenile central bearded dragons from different hatches were included in the study and housed together at the start of the observation period. The group consisted of two females and one male, all approximately eight weeks of age at the onset of the study. Female A was a standard (classic) morph, tan and brown in coloration. Female B was a hypomelanistic morph, yellow and orange in coloration. The male was a dunner morph with orange coloration and blue-gray patterning. Two individuals were purchased from a commercial pet retailer, and the male was adopted from the same retailer after sustaining a minor tail injury from a conspecific. The injury had healed prior to the study, and the animal was examined and cleared by a veterinarian, with no signs of infection observed.

Housing and Husbandry

The dragons were initially cohabitated in a 75-gallon enclosure arranged to accommodate shared use. The enclosure contained three separate basking sites, climbing branches, and multiple hides to allow for resting and retreat. Appropriate ultraviolet B (UVB) lighting was provided and distributed evenly across the enclosure, along with a heat lamp to maintain suitable basking temperatures. Temperature and humidity were monitored daily to ensure conditions remained within recommended ranges for the species. Shared resources were intentionally provided to observe tolerance and space use under cohabitation conditions. During the seventh month of observation, the male was removed from the enclosure due to the onset of reproductive behaviors and concerns for female welfare.

Feeding and Supplementation

The dragons were fed regularly throughout the study. The diet consisted primarily of live insects, including dubia roaches (*Blaptica dubia*), crickets, black soldier fly larvae, and appropriately sized superworms. Vegetables were also provided in the form of mixed salads containing kale, carrot, zucchini, green pepper, yellow squash, green beans, and dandelion greens. Calcium and multivitamin supplements were added to food as part of routine husbandry. Bee pollen was occasionally used to encourage consumption of plant material. Calcium supplementation was increased for the females during periods of gravidity.

Behavioral Observations

Behavioral observations were conducted daily throughout the study using direct, ad libitum observation and were qualitative and descriptive in nature, with individuals monitored multiple times per day during morning, afternoon, and evening periods. Behaviors were defined in advance using an ethogram (Table 1) and included social displays (e.g., head bobbing and black

bearding), basking behavior, feeding interactions, and indicators of social tolerance, including spatial positioning during conspecific approach events.

Table 1

Ethogram of social and individual behaviors observed in captive bearded dragons

Behavior	Description
Approach	Individual moves toward another within approximately one body length
Retreat/Avoidance	Individual increases distance or vacates position following approach or display by another conspecific
Displacement	One individual takes basking/food/hide position; the other vacates within ~5–10 seconds
Head bobbing	Repeated vertical head movements directed toward a conspecific during social interactions
Head bowing	Slow lowering and holding of the head directed toward a conspecific during close social interactions
Arm waving	Slow, circular movement of one forelimb directed toward a conspecific
Foot Stomping	Repeated lifting and forceful placement of one or more forelimbs against the substrate during social interactions
Black bearding	Beard darkening and/or expansion during social interaction
Tongue flicking/ Tongue touching	Repeated protrusion of the tongue toward a conspecific, substrate, or enclosure surface during social or investigative interactions
Blocking/Interposition	Individual positions body between a conspecific and another individual, orienting toward the approaching conspecific and maintaining position until the approach ceases
Tail Whipping	Rapid lateral movement of the tail directed toward a conspecific during close interaction
Bite attempt	Open-mouth snap or lunge directed toward a conspecific, with or without contact

Aggressive interaction	Escalated social interaction involving tail whipping, bite attempts, or physical contact
Basking—alone	Stationary in basking zone without physical contact with conspecific
Basking—shared	Two or more individuals occupying the same basking site simultaneously without aggression
Feeding interactions— taking turns	Sequential feeding behavior in which individuals alternate access to food items without aggression
Feeding interactions— food displacement	Removal of a food item from another individual’s mouth or immediate feeding space
Co-feeding (salad)	Simultaneous feeding by multiple individuals from the same food source without aggressive interaction
Sleeping—cohabitation	Two or more individuals resting together under the same hide or in physical contact during inactive periods
Glass surfing	Repetitive pacing/scratching along enclosure glass surfaces

Growth Measurements

Body mass was measured in grams using a digital kitchen scale. Measurements were recorded monthly for each individual throughout the 13-month study period.

Ethical Considerations

All animals were privately owned and maintained under standard captive husbandry practices. No invasive procedures were performed during the study. The male was removed from cohabitation when stress-related behaviors were observed to prioritize animal welfare. The health and well-being of all individuals were monitored continuously and prioritized throughout the study.

Results

Body mass was recorded monthly to assess growth patterns and monitor development throughout the study period. Body mass increased steadily for all individuals over the 13-month observation period. Female B exhibited slower weight gain during mid-development; however, body mass increased more rapidly later in the study. No abrupt declines in body mass were observed for any individual. Changes in body mass over time for all three individuals are shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. *Body mass changes over time in three captive bearded dragons over a 13-month period.*

During the initial months of cohabitation, no overt aggression was observed among the three bearded dragons. Individuals alternated basking locations and occasionally shared basking sites without conflict. No dominance displays or visible stress-related behaviors were observed during this period. After approximately 6–7 months of cohabitation, the male began exhibiting dominance-related behaviors, including head bobbing and black bearding (see Table 1). An

unfamiliar adult bearded dragon occasionally approached the enclosure during this time. In response, the male consistently descended from elevated basking sites and displayed head bobbing, foot stomping, and black bearding directed toward the approaching individual. When the unfamiliar dragon approached areas of the enclosure occupied by the females, the male positioned himself between the females and the enclosure boundary while displaying similar behaviors.

The male was removed from the enclosure during month seven following increased dominance and reproductive behaviors. After removal, the two females continued to cohabitate without observable aggression and continued to share basking sites. Short-term reintroductions were conducted during the remaining months of the study, primarily during feeding and occasional basking periods. During these reintroductions, all individuals tolerated one another for brief periods of up to approximately 30 minutes, after which the male resumed dominance and reproductive behaviors. When the unfamiliar adult bearded dragon was present during reintroduction periods, the male continued to display dominance behaviors directed toward the unfamiliar individual and positioned himself between the females when the unfamiliar dragon approached. At no point during the study were the animals allowed to engage in physical conflict or sustain injury.

Discussion

The results of this study indicate that juvenile bearded dragons were able to cohabitate for several months without overt aggression, with social dynamics shifting markedly as sexual maturity was reached. The onset of dominance and reproductive behaviors in the male during

month seven necessitated his removal, after which the two females continued to cohabitate successfully. Notably, the females did not exhibit increased dominance or stress toward one another during gravidity, and selective dominance behaviors appeared to be context-dependent rather than persistent.

These findings are consistent with emerging literature suggesting that bearded dragons, while not obligately social, may exhibit social tolerance under certain conditions. In captive environments, the absence of predation and reduced competition for resources may alter ecological pressures that otherwise promote solitary behavior in the wild. Rather than requiring complex social structures, reptile sociality may be expressed through tolerance, familiarity, and context-specific interactions. This supports the idea that behavior can play an important role beyond genetic predisposition, particularly under novel environmental conditions (Brakes et al., 2019).

Observational evidence from this study further suggests that bearded dragons are capable of adapting their behavior over time, accommodating changes in social context, and recognizing familiar individuals even following periods of separation (Leal & Powell, 2012; Wilkinson et al., 2025).

Behavioral changes observed during months six and seven coincided with the male reaching sexual maturity and increasing dominance displays. The decision to remove the male from the enclosure was driven by welfare considerations, as his presence led to increased avoidance and retreat behaviors in the females, including retreating to hides and reduced spatial use. Prolonged exposure to such stressors could have resulted in adverse health outcomes, underscoring why cohabitation, particularly involving males, is commonly discouraged in bearded dragons (Vitt & Caldwell, 2013). While male–female cohabitation became limited following sexual maturation,

female–female cohabitation remained stable throughout the remainder of the study, suggesting that sex-specific dynamics play a critical role in social tolerance.

The ethogram provides a framework for identifying subtle social and tolerance-related behaviors that preceded overt aggression or physiological change. Importantly, behavioral changes were observed prior to any measurable physiological decline, emphasizing the value of behavioral monitoring in captive husbandry. Reliance on rigid husbandry rules, such as blanket recommendations against all cohabitation, may oversimplify the complexity of reptile behavior. Subtle behavioral indicators can reflect stress, and welfare concerns even in the absence of overt aggression. Previous studies have shown that bearded dragons may exhibit anxiety-related behaviors under gentle handling conditions, reinforcing the importance of close behavioral observation when managing captive reptiles (Stockley et al., 2020). Captive observational studies also provide opportunities to improve husbandry practices and assess welfare outcomes, including in individuals with physical impairments, which have been shown to adapt behaviorally to enrichment and environmental conditions (Pereira et al., 2024).

This study is limited by its small sample size and observational design, which restrict the generalizability of the findings. Future research would benefit from larger sample sizes, controlled comparisons, and sex-specific experimental designs to further examine social tolerance and dominance dynamics in bearded dragons. Longitudinal studies incorporating standardized behavioral measures could strengthen understanding of how social interactions change across developmental stages. While these findings do not advocate routine cohabitation of bearded dragons, they suggest that under carefully monitored conditions, limited social tolerance and familiarity-based interactions may occur in captivity. Any decision to cohabitate

individuals should be approached cautiously, with continuous monitoring for behavioral changes indicative of stress or declining welfare.

Conclusion

This longitudinal observational study demonstrates that juvenile bearded dragons can exhibit temporary social tolerance when raised together in captivity, with social dynamics shifting as individuals reach sexual maturity. While early cohabitation occurred without overt aggression or growth suppression, the emergence of dominance and reproductive behaviors in the male necessitated separation to maintain welfare. Female–female cohabitation remained stable throughout the study, even during periods of gravidity, highlighting the importance of sex-specific social dynamics. These findings emphasize that bearded dragon behavior in captivity is context-dependent and may differ from traditional assumptions of strict solitary behavior. Behavioral monitoring proved critical, as changes in behavior preceded any physiological decline. Although limited in sample size, this study contributes to a growing body of evidence suggesting that captive reptile social behavior is more flexible than previously recognized and underscores the need for cautious, observation-based husbandry practices.

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